

Cannabinoids Based On Therapeutics

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ABSTRACT

There is a growing interest in the use of cannabis (and its extracts), as well as CBD oil (hemp extracts containing cannabidiol), for therapeutic purposes. While there is reason to believe that cannabinoids may be efficacious for a number of different diseases and syndromes, there exist limited objective data supporting the use of crude materials (CBD oil, cannabis extracts, and/or cannabis itself). In the present review, we examined data for pure cannabinoid compounds (dronabinol, nabilone, and CBD), as well as partially purified medicinal cannabis extracts (nabiximols), to provide guidance on the potential therapeutic uses of high-THC cannabis and CBD oil. In general, data support a role for cannabis/cannabinoids in pain, seizure disorders, appetite stimulation, muscle spasticity, and treatment of nausea/vomiting. Given the biological activities of the cannabinoids, there may be utility in treatment of central nervous system disorders (such as neurodegenerative diseases, PTSD, and addiction) or for the treatment of cancer.

Keywords: On balance, there are reasons to support the potential use of medical cannabis and cannabis extract (Δ^9 -THC-dominant or CBD-dominant), but much more careful research is required.

Cannabinoid signaling pathways and effects

INTRODUCTION

Cannabinoids are a family of unique compounds synthesized by cannabis sativa (marijuana) that have not been found as yet in any other plant. The main representative cannabinoid, owing to its high abundance in the plant and its strong biological activity, is Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (THC). The word cannabinoid refers to every chemical substance, regardless of structure or origin, that joins the cannabinoid receptors of the body and brain and that have similar effects to those produced by the Cannabis Sativa plant. The three types of cannabinoids that people use are recreational, medicinal and synthetic.

History

The existence of cannabinoid receptors in the brain was discovered from invitro studies in 1980s, with the receptor type 1 or CB1. The DNA sequence that encodes a G-protein- coupled cannabinoid receptor in the human brain was identified and cloned in 1990. These discoveries led to determination in 1993 of a second brain cannabinoid receptor named cannabinoid receptor type 2 or CB2. Cannabis has a long and colorful history. The use of cannabis originated in central Asia or western China. Cannabis has been used for its alleged healing properties for millennia. The first documented case of its use dates back to 2800BC, when it was listed in the Emperor Shen Ning's (regarded as the father of Chinese medicine) pharmacopeia. Therapeutic indications of cannabis are mentioned in the texts of the Indian Hindus, Assyrians, Greeks and Romans.

TYPES OF CANNABINOIDS

The three types of cannabinoids that people use are

Recreational

Medicinal

Synthetic

Research has found that the cannabis plant produces between 80 and 100 cannabinoids and about 300 non-cannabinoid chemicals. The two main cannabinoids are delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) and cannabidiol (CBD).

Mechanism of Action

Cannabinoids function by stimulating two receptor, cannabinoid receptor type 1 (CB1) and type 2 (CB2), within the endocannabinoid system. This system is a complex network of organs throughout the body, expressing the cannabinoid receptors and playing a homeostatic role. These would reach presynaptic neurons by activating and inducing the expression of CB1 receptor, which, in turn, inhibit voltage-gated calcium channel and activate potassium channels. The result is restriction of the excitatory neurotransmitters release²⁸. Pharmacology of cannabinoid CB1 and CB2 receptors.

Cannabinoids Healthy Benefit

A detailed discussion of the endocannabinoid system and its potential utility in pharmacotherapy was presented in 2006; however, a plethora of new data have become available in recent years [21, 67]. Indeed, there are currently many ongoing clinical trials of Δ^9 -THC, CBD, and other cannabinoids reported on the FDA Clinical Trials. gov website. As of this writing, a search for CBD yielded 352 trials, , and NCT04734080). A review of the identified studies suggests novel avenues for the treatment of, or at least symptomatic control for, various disease states. For many diseases, there is growing evidence that suggests clinical potential for Δ^9 -THC and/ or CBD; however, there are few evidence-based, placebo-controlled studies for smokable and/or edible cannabis.

Diseases of the Central Nervous System

Multiple Sclerosis

It is a progressive demyelinating disease. Patients with MS have been found to have changes in the expression of CB1 and CB2 receptors, and this may account for therapeutic potential of cannabis-derived products. Sativex is approved in several countries for the treatment of spasticity associated with MS. Additionally, Δ^9 -THC alone was found to be ineffective in the management of this condition by the multi-year CUPID study

Epilepsy

A chronic condition of recurrent seizures often presents in childhood and arises out of abnormal excitation inhibition balance of neurons in the brain. Cannabinoids may act as neuroprotective agents and may also reduce inflammatory responses in patients with epilepsy. Clinically, cannabidiol seems to have greater efficacy than whole-plant cannabis for the treatment of epileptic seizures as case reports and surveys have described smoked cannabis as having both pro- and anti-convulsant properties.

Adverse Effect

Adverse Effects of Cannabinoids According to the US Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, the proportion of developing adolescents (ages 12–17) in the USA who are current high-THC cannabis users has remained the same (at 7.4%) over the last decade. However, this same study also notes a recent uptick in the use of this substance among older individuals. Therefore, if the connection between parental drinking and adolescent drinking holds true for other substances of abuse, this uptick may foreshadow later increases in illicit marijuana consumption among this particularly vulnerable population. This is especially worrying as emerging evidence indicates serious contraindications for heavy cannabis use by adolescents. Moreover, there is growing concern for the emergence of cannabis-induced hyperemesis syndrome, or uncontrolled vomiting, observed in both adolescents and adults. A further complication is the fact that there seems to have been a marketplace race (in jurisdictions with legalized recreational cannabis) to provide products with higher and higher Δ^9 -THC levels and with lower and lower CBD.

Adverse Effects on Cognition and Development

As described above, endocannabinoids have an important role in tempering neuronal excitability through modulation of the release of the GABA and glutamate neurotransmitters. The disruption of these processes, such as through exposure to high doses of exogenous cannabinoids prior to the age of sixteen, has been implicated in the arrest of cortical maturation due to the dysregulation of nerve connection potentiation and brain plasticity. When paired with research that links reduced mitochondrial activity with cannabis use and poor memory formation, these data serve to explain the drop of ~2– 6 IQ points that has been observed from childhood to adulthood in persistent cannabis users. Notably, this drop in neuropsychological function is not fully reversed with cessation of the drug, and this was observed even when years of education, alcohol use, and other drug dependences were considered. More acutely, in regard to memory, intravenous Δ^9 -THC administration in the amount of 0.03 mg/kg, or about 2.4 mg for the average North American, inhibits the encoding of verbal information and significantly decreases immediate and delayed recall in a broad spectrum of ages.

Pathophysiology:

The most potent cannabinoid, THC, was isolated in the 1960s. Nearly 3 decades later, in the early 1990s, the specific cannabinoid receptors were discovered, CB1 (or Cnr1) and CB2 (or Cnr2). The CB1 receptors are predominantly located in the brain, with a wide distribution. The highest densities are found in the frontal cerebral cortex (higher functioning), hippocampus (memory, cognition), basal ganglion and cerebellum (movement), and striatum (brain reward). Other brain regions in which the CB1 receptors are found include areas responsible for anxiety, pain, sensory perception, motor coordination, and endocrine function. This distribution is consistent with the clinical effects elicited by cannabinoids.

The CB2 receptor, on the other hand, is located peripherally. Specifically, it is involved in the immune system (splenic macrophages, T and B lymphocytes), peripheral nerves, and the vas deferens.

Potency

In recent decades, the average THC potency of cannabis has increased due to more sophisticated plant breeding and cultivation.^[3] In the 1970s, the average marijuana cigarette contained approximately 10 mg of THC. Currently, a comparable cigarette contains 60-150 mg. Because the effects of THC are dose dependent, modern cannabis users may experience greater morbidity than their predecessors.

Cannabis is available in several forms. Marijuana is a combination of the cannabis flowering tops and leaves. The THC content is 0.5-5%. Two preparations are possible:

- Bhang – Dried leaves and tops
- Ganja – Leaves and tops with a higher resin content, which results in greater potency

Hashish is dried resin collected from the flowering tops. The THC concentration is 2-20%. Hash oil is a liquid extract; it contains 15% THC.

Absorption

The route of administration determines the absorption of the cannabis product, as follows:

- Smoking – Onset of action is rapid (within minutes); it results in 10-35% absorption of the available THC; peak plasma concentrations occur within 8 minutes.
- Ingestion – Onset occurs within 1-3 hours (unpredictable); 5-20% is absorbed, due to stomach acid content and metabolism; peak plasma levels occur 2-6 hours after ingestion.

Behavioral effects

THC most commonly produces euphoria, or a "high," including feelings of intoxication and detachment, relaxation, altered perception of time and distance, intensified sensory experiences, laughter, talkativeness, decreased anxiety, decreased alertness, and depression. These effects depend on the dose, expectations of the user, mode of administration, social environment, and personality.

Cardiovascular effects

These include the following:

- Naive users may experience a sudden 20-100% rise in heart rate, lasting up to 2-3 hours
- Peripheral vasodilatation causes postural hypotension, which may lead to dizziness or syncope
- Cardiac output increases by as much as 30%, and cardiac oxygen demand is also increased; tolerance to these effects can develop within a few days of use
- Naive users can experience angina; in addition, users with preexisting coronary artery disease or cerebrovascular disease may experience myocardial infarctions, congestive heart failure, and strokes

Respiratory effects

Transient bronchodilatation may occur after an acute exposure. With chronic heavy smoking, users experience increased cough, sputum production, and wheezing. These complaints are augmented by concurrent tobacco use. One study cites that the rate of decline of respiratory function in an 8-year period was greater among marijuana smokers than among tobacco smokers.

Aside from nicotine, marijuana cigarettes contain some of the same components as tobacco smoke, including bronchial irritants, tumor initiators (mutagens), and tumor promoters. The amount of tar in a marijuana cigarette is 3 times the amount in a tobacco cigarette when smoked, with one-third greater deposition in the respiratory tract.

Chronic cannabis use is associated with bronchitis, squamous metaplasia of the tracheobronchial epithelium, and emphysema. These problems have been reported more frequently in cannabis-only users than in tobacco-only users.

Dependence and withdrawal

Nearly 7-10% of regular users become behaviorally and physically dependent on cannabis. Furthermore, early onset of use and daily/weekly use correlates with future dependence. According to the National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA), 100,000 people are treated annually for primary (may be self-perceived) marijuana abuse.

Animal studies demonstrate withdrawal symptoms with use of CB1 receptor antagonists. However, in humans, the withdrawal syndrome is not well characterized. Classic manifestations—which may develop upon withdrawal after as little as 1 week of daily use—include the following

- Irritability
- Restlessness
- Insomnia
- Anorexia
- Nausea
- Sweating
- Salivation
- **P**Increased body temperature
- Tremors

SYMPTOMS OF WEED OVERDOSE

- Extreme anxiety
- Racing pulse
- Hallucinations
- Panic attacks
- Impaired coordination and motor skills
- Increased heart rate
- Dry mouth and throat
- Red eyes
- Distorted perception of time

DRUG INTERACTION

USE DOSE LEVEL:

LEVEL	THC PER DOSE	EXPECT RANGE
Micro dose	1-2.5mg	This is a great dose for beginners. You will feel relaxed but not intoxicated.
Light	3-5mg	This dose is good for those who want a little more of a buzz but not strong where they can still function.
Medium	10-15mg	This dose is for those a bit more experienced and greater for a nice hike or adventure. You feel high with this dose if this is not your goal stick with a smaller dose.
High	20-30mg	This is great dose for experienced THC users. You feel a nice balanced high, not too much but also not too little.
Very High	50-100mg	This dose is for stoners. You are already used to cannabis and you love the relaxing and intoxicating effects of THC.
Macrodome	100-500mg	This dose is for the very experienced and should only be used if you worked your way up to this point. This is a very intense high and should be used with extreme caution.

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